

EARTHQUAKE GENERATION POTENTIAL ALONG THE DIFFERENT SEGMENTS OF THE PHILIPPINE FAULT IN EASTERN MINDANAO, PHILIPPINES

Jeffrey S. Perez¹ and Hiroyuki Tsutsumi²

¹Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology – Department of Science and Technology (PHIVOLCS-DOST) ²Department of Geophysics, Kyoto University

ABSTRACT: The Philippine fault is one of the major earthquake sources in the Philippines that had generated large damaging earthquakes in the past four centuries. This 1250-km-long left-lateral strike-slip fault traverses the entire Philippine archipelago from northwestern Luzon Island in the north to eastern Mindanao in the south. In this paper, we will discuss the earthquake generation potential along the mapped Philippine fault segments in eastern Mindanao. These fault segments range from 20 to 100 km in length and are capable of generating earthquakes of M_w 6.6 to M_w 7.4. Within this magnitude range, we expect strong ground shaking that could significantly damage eastern Mindanao similar to historical events, namely: 1879 M_w 7.4 Surigao earthquake, 1891 M_s 7.3 Davao earthquake and 1893 M_s 7.2 Monkayo earthquake. The results of this study may serve as an essential inputs for seismic hazard assessment in this part of the country.

KEYWORDS: format; proceedings; conference; earthquake engineering; Word

KEYWORDS: active tectonics, fault segmentation, seismic hazard assessment, paleoseismology, earthquake scenario

1. INTRODUCTION

The Philippine fault is one of the major earthquake generators not only in the Philippines but also in the world (Figure 1). This active fault is comparable to other major strike-slip faults such as the San Andreas fault in California, USA (Sieh 1978a; 1978b), the Median Tectonic Line in Japan (Tsutsumi and Okada 1996), the North Anatolian fault in Turkey (Jolivet and Faccenna 2000; McClusky, et al. 2000) and the Sumatran fault in Indonesia (Sieh and Natawidjaja 2000). The Philippine fault is about 1250-km-long and traverses the entire Philippine archipelago from northern Luzon Island in the north to eastern Mindanao in the south (Allen 1962; Aurelio 2000; Barrier et al. 1991; Tsutsumi and Perez 2013). This NNW-trending, arc-parallel fault is a result of the oblique subduction of the northwest moving Philippine Sea plate beneath the Philippine archipelago (Figure 1). The structural and geometric features of the Philippine fault has been identified since the middle of last century and studies have been conducted to describe its structural characteristics but more detailed studies should be done to better understand its surface-rupturing behavior, recurrence interval and earthquake generation potential.

The Philippine fault has been a major source of large damaging earthquake in the country and has been seismically active for the past 200 years with more than 10 earthquakes

greater than magnitude 7 (Bautista and Oike 2000) (Figure 1). One of the largest and most destructive was the 1990 Mw 7.7 Luzon earthquake accompanied by about 120-km-long surface-rupture with 6 m maximum left-lateral horizontal displacement (Nakata et al. 1996). Other recent surface-rupturing earthquakes along the Philippine fault are the 1973 M_L 7.0 Ragay Gulf earthquake (Morante 1974) and the 2003 M_s 6.2 Masbate earthquake (PHIVOLCS Quick Response Team 2003). The high seismic potential of this fault can also be identified from campaign-type GPS observations that revealed a very high slip rates ranging from 20-30 mm/yr along the different segments (Aurelio 2000). From the perspective of a seismic risk assessment, there is a need to study the Philippine fault because this structure traverses through or are close to major population and economic center of the country.

Using available large-scale aerial photographs and active tectonics studies, Tsutsumi and Perez (2013) have mapped the 90% of the surface trace of the Philippine fault in a 1:50000-scale topographic map. They have described the geometry, distribution and characteristics of the Philippine fault in major islands in the Philippines (Luzon, Masbate, Leyte and Mindanao) (Figure 1). Tsutsumi and Perez (2013) also discussed the along-strike variation in fault trace geometry wherein they have suggested that the Philippine fault in central Luzon and Mindanao Islands is highly segmented and can generate earthquakes with magnitudes greater than 7. In comparison, the fault trace in Masbate and Leyte Islands are more continuous and based on historical seismicity, there was no earthquake greater than magnitude 7 for the past 400 years (Bautista and Oike 2000).

Just like other major strike-slip faults in the world, the Philippine fault is generally not continuous and do not rupture their entire length in a single earthquake. This is a characteristic of strike-slip faults that they tend to rupture individual fault segments (fault segmentation) and is also observed in world's major strike-slip faults. Surface rupture may happen along a single segment with its own surface-rupture history or it may extend to multiple segments (Schwartz and Coppersmith 1984).

Classification of fault segmentation may be geometric or structural and temporal. Geometric or structural segmentation is based mainly on the physical characteristic of the fault trace. It is characterized by changes in surface fault geometry such as changes in strike, step overs, bifurcations and fault bends or gaps. On the other hand, temporal fault segmentation are based on coseismic behavior revealed in historical surface-rupture and paleoseismic studies (Schwartz and Coppersmith 1984). In terms of reliability, temporal segmentation is more reliable method for fault segmentation compared to geometric or structural segmentation but historical and paleoseismic information are either insufficient or difficult to obtain in most active faults. Studies of recent surface-rupturing earthquakes (e.g. 2002 M_w 7.6 Denali earthquake, 1991 M_w 7.1 Izmit earthquake and 1990 M_w 7.7 Luzon earthquake) suggest that mapped complexities in surface fault geometry influence the nucleation and termination of faulting processes (Wesnousky 2006).

Fault segmentation studies have been conducted on other strike-slip faults of the world such as the San Andreas fault (Wallace 1990), the Median Tectonic Line (Tsutsumi and Okada 1996), the North Anatolian fault (Sengör et al. 2005) and the Sumatran fault (Sieh and Natawidjaja 2000). Perez et al. (2015) have proposed segmentation of the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao based on geometric segmentation criteria and integrating paleoseismic and geological information from previous studies. In this paper, we will

briefly discuss the distribution and segmentation of the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao and evaluate its earthquake generation potential. These information are very important for medium to long-term seismic risk assessment in this part of the county.

Figure 1. Tectonic setting of the Philippines. Map showing the tectonic structures in the Philippines, the Philippine fault (solid black line, Tsutsumi and Perez 2013) and epicenters (circles) of moderate to large magnitude earthquakes (Bautista and Oike 2000).

2. THE PHILIPPINE FAULT IN EASTERN MINDANAO

Located on the southern part of the archipelago, Mindanao Island is the second largest island in the Philippines. The Philippine fault traverses the eastern part of this island and has been the least studied segment compared to other segments of the Philippine fault. It enters onshore, west of Surigao City, and traverses the eastern portion of Mindanao for about 320 km southward to Mati City (Figure 2). Mapping of the surface trace is mainly based on remote sensing images such as Landsat, SPOT, radar and aerial photographs and has revealed that the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao is restricted to a well-defined narrow deformation zone (Quebral et al. 1996). Tsutsumi and Perez (2013) mapped the entire Philippine fault using aerial photograph and field investigation and they suggested that the Philippine fault is composed of several segments divided by geometric discontinuities such as steps and branching.

Most of the seismic events recorded in eastern Mindanao are located offshore due to the subduction of the Philippine Sea plate along the Philippine trench (Figure 1) while on-land seismicity are attributed to the movement along the different segments of the Philippine fault and to other nearby active faults. Historical documents revealed possible surface-rupturing earthquakes along the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao such as the 1879 Mw 7.4 Surigao earthquake, 1891 Ms 7.2 Davao earthquake and the 1893 Ms 7.3 Monkayo earthquake (Bautista and Oike 2000; Perez et al. 2015). In terms of slip rate, GPS results indicate a northward increase in slip rate along the Philippine fault from 10 mm/yr in Davao to 24 mm/yr in Surigao (Aurelio 2000).

3. THE PHILIPPINE FAULT SEGMENTS IN EASTERN MINDANAO AND ITS EARTHQUAKE GENERATION POTENTIAL

To better characterize the location, geometry and distribution of the Philippine fault in this part of the Philippines, Perez et al. (2015) interpreted additional aerial photos, conducted detailed geomorphic mapping, paleoseismic studies and review of historical earthquake documents. They have identified nine individual fault segments (Figure 2) ranging from 20 to 100 km by considering geometric segmentation together with new geological and paleoseismic information and analysis of historical surface-rupturing earthquakes. In the following sections, we will briefly describe the segments of the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao as described by Perez et al. (2015) from north to south and discuss the earthquake generation potential for each segment or the moment magnitude of the maximum credible earthquake for each segment by using the empirical relation suggested by Wells and Coppersmith (1994). Figure 2 shows the segments of the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao while Table 1 summarizes the segment length, magnitude of the maximum credible earthquake and historical earthquakes for each segment of the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao.

3.1 Surigao segment

From Leyte Island, the Philippine fault traverses Mindanao Sea and enters Mindanao Island west of Surigao City (Figure 2). The Surigao segment is fairly continuous for about 100 km. It traverses the eastern margin of Malimono Ridge for about 30 km and traverses Lake Mainit in Surigao Del Norte and Agusan del Norte for about 20 km. The general strike along this portion of the fault is N15°-20°W.

Figure 2. Map showing the segments of the Philippine fault (black line; revised from Perez et al. 2015) in eastern Mindanao and epicenters (circles; Bautista and Oike 2000) of surface-rupturing earthquakes. The following are the segments of the Philippine in this area (Perez et al. 2015): A. Surigao; B. Esperanza; C. Agusan

**Marsh; D. West Compostela Valley (WCV); E. Central Compostela Valley (CCV);
F. Nabunturan; G. East Compostela Valley (ECV); H. Caraga River and I. Mati.**

South of Lake Mainit, Perez et al. (in preparation) identified a continuous 10-km-long, east facing tectonic scarp about 0.5-1.0 m high traversing the central portion of Tubay Valley. This tectonic scarp strikes N20°W. Based on their aerial photograph interpretation, geomorphic mapping, paleoseismic studies and historical documents, they have concluded that this tectonic scarp is attributed to the surface-rupture of the 1879 M_w 7.4 Surigao earthquake. It is very difficult to map the continuity of the fault trace south of Tubay Valley because the tectonic geomorphic features were buried by recent sedimentation along an active river system. The fault trace continues for about 35 km along recent alluvial fans at the western edge of the Eastern Mindanao Ridge.

At the southern end of the Surigao segment, east of Butuan City, the fault trace changes its strike significantly from N15°-20°W to N20°-30°W and the fault branches as it traverses the western edge of Eastern Mindanao Ridge. The fault trace continues for about 10 km. The branching of the fault to the south and the changes in the strike lead us to identify the southern end of the Surigao segment near the western edge of Eastern Mindanao Ridge.

The total length of the Surigao segment is about 100 km and most probably ruptured its entire length during the 1879 M_w 7.4 Surigao earthquake. Using the relationship of surface length and moment magnitude suggested by Wells and Coppersmith (1994), the maximum credible earthquake of this segment is M_w 7.4.

3.2 Esperanza segment

At the western edge of Eastern Mindanao Ridge and to the south of the Surigao segment is a continuous fault trace, the Esperanza segment, that extends for about 50 km in Agusan Marsh (Figure 2) and generally trends N15°-20°W (Perez et al. 2015). The northern part of this segment is difficult to map because of dense vegetation in the mountains. From here, the fault exits the mountain ridge and enters the Agusan Marsh with a little change along the strike. In the vicinity of Esperanza, Agusan del Sur, Perez et al. (2015) mapped a continuous scarp, most probably a result of recent surface-rupturing earthquake. This east-facing continuous scarp is about 8-km-long with about 1 m vertical scarp and traverses the wide alluvial plain of the Agusan River and the northern part of the Agusan Marsh.

Perez et al. (2015) reviewed the historical and instrumental seismicity for the last 400 years and they have not identified historical surface-rupturing earthquake related to this segment. At the southern end of the Esperanza segment, the fault trace steps to the left for about 1 km (restraining step) and steps to the right for about 3 km (releasing step) north of Talacogon. Based on Wells and Coppersmith (1994) surface length and earthquake magnitude relationship, the 50-km-long Esperanza segment can generate an earthquake of M_w 7.1.

3.3 Agusan Marsh segment

South of the Esperanza segment is the 65-km-long Agusan Marsh segment that cuts through the Agusan Marsh (Figure 2). Agusan Marsh is a depression and is part of the wide alluvial plain of the Agusan River. It is bounded in the east by the Eastern Mindanao Ridge and in the west by the Central Mindanao Ridge. Perez et al. (2015) mapped the extent of

the Agusan Marsh segment using aerial photographs and there is difficulty in mapping the fault trace in the field because most of the fault traces are submerged under water. The 65-km-long Esperanza segment extends for about 65 km from Talacogon to Veruela and generally strikes N10°-15°W. Based on aerial photograph interpretation the fault trace is fairly continuous, there is no systematic direction for the downthrown side and in some areas Perez et al. (2015) mapped parallel fault trace and steps that results to tectonic depression as manifested by sag ponds or lakes (e.g. Lake Lumao).

Historical seismicity for the past 400 years indicates that there were no surface-rupturing earthquakes that can be attributed to this segment. The fault segment may extend at the edge of Mount Olagusan (western edge of Eastern Mindanao Ridge) and the left-stepping en echelon faults with at least 5 km steps indicates the southern termination of the Agusan Marsh segment. The 65-km-long Agusan Marsh segment may generate a M_w 7.2 earthquake (Wells and Coppersmith 1994) if the entire segment will rupture. South of this segment are several north-trending left-stepping fault strands that comprise the next four segments (West Compostela Valley, Central Compostela Valley, Nabunturan and East Compostela Valley segments).

Table 1. Summary of segment lengths, magnitudes of maximum credible earthquake and historical earthquakes for the different Philippine fault segments in eastern Mindanao

Segment Name	Segment Length (km)	Magnitude of Maximum Credible Earthquake (M_w)	Historical Earthquake
A. Surigao	100	7.4	1879 M_w 7.4 Surigao Earthquake
B. Esperanza	50	7.1	
C. Agusan Marsh	65	7.2	
D. West Compostela Valley (CCV)	55	7.1	1891 M_s 7.3 Davao Earthquake
E. Central Compostela Valley (CCV)	60	7.1	1893 M_s 7.2 Monkayo Earthquake
F. Nabunturan	25	6.7	
G. East Compostela Valley (ECV)	20	6.6	
H. Caraga River	35	6.9	
I. Mati	60	7.1	

3.4 West Compostela Valley (WCV) segment

Compostela Valley is a 20-km-wide valley and is bounded in the west by the Central Mindanao Ridge (which includes the Olagusán and Jaguimitán Mountains) and in the east by the Eastern Mindanao Ridge. In this valley, the Philippine fault is manifested by several north-south trending, left-stepping en echelon fault strands (Figure 2).

Perez et al. (2015) identified the West Compostela Valley (WCV) segment as the westernmost strand that extends from the eastern edge of the northern Mount Olagusán to the eastern edge of the Central Mindanao Ridge near the municipality of the Mawab, Compostela Valley Province. This segment of the Philippine fault is about 55 km and generally trends N-S to N5°W (Figure 2). The fault trace in this segment was mapped using aerial photograph and is manifested by linear tectonic scarp traversing the mountain range with offset creeks. Small left steps and branching were identified in the north and the segment ends abruptly in the south without branching and steps. Near the southern end of this fault segment, east of Mawab, a 5-km fault strand was also mapped with a general strike of N30°-35°W.

A review of historical seismicity in this area revealed that a probable surface-rupturing earthquake may have occurred along this segment. Historical documents of the 1891 M_s 7.2 Davao earthquake mentioned long and wide fissures in the hills. Bautista and Oike (2000) identified that the epicenter of this earthquake was in the Central Mindanao Ridge (north of Davao). It is difficult to conclude if the long and wide fissures were the surface-rupture of the 1891 Davao earthquake because these features may also indicate landslides in the mountains. It is also possible that the 1891 Davao earthquake is accompanied by surface-rupture but people at that time may have difficulty in recognizing and documenting the feature because the fault traverses a highly vegetated mountain.

Using the relationship of surface length and moment magnitude suggested by Wells and Coppersmith (1994), the maximum credible earthquake for the WCV segment is M_w 7.1 and probably ruptured during the 1891 M_s 7.2 Davao earthquake.

3.5 Central Compostela Valley (CCV) segment

At the boundary of the northern part of Mount Jaguimitán, several left-stepping en echelon faults (5 to 10-km-long) were mapped east of the WCV segment. One of the most distinct fault strand is the 60-km-long, north-south trending, Central Compostela Valley (CCV) segment (Figure 2). Along this segment, Perez et al. (2015) mapped a 10-km-long east-facing tectonic scarp and identified offset creeks in the northern part of the CCV segment. Based on paleoseismic investigation conducted by Perez and Tsutsumi (in preparation), the mapped tectonic scarp is attributed to the surface rupture of the 1893 M_s 7.3 Monkayo earthquake. The termination of this segment to the south is manifested by three right-stepping en echelon faults with lengths of less than 5 km and one left-stepping fault (about 5-km-wide restraining step). The left-stepping fault, the Caraga River segment, extends further to the south and traverses the Eastern Mindanao Ridge up to the Tagub Mountains.

Based on Wells and Coppersmith (1994), surface length and earthquake magnitude relationship, the 60-km-long CCV segment can generate an earthquake of M_w 7.1 and ruptured during the 1893 M_s 7.3 Monkayo earthquake.

3.6 Nabunturan segment

Along the middle portion of the CCV segment, a fault branches to the west and identified as the Nabunturan segment of the Philippine fault (Figure 2). This fault segment is about 25-km-long and bounds the eastern edge of Mount Jaguimitan which is part of the Central Mindanao Ridge. Most of the mapped tectonic scarps of the Nabunturan segment are west-facing and generally trends $N5^{\circ}$ - 15° E which is different compared to the other north-south trending segments of the Philippine fault in Compostela Valley (Perez et al. 2015). Historical seismicity on this area revealed that there are no surface-rupturing earthquakes attributed to this segment. The Nabunturan segment is capable of generating a M_w 6.7 earthquake (Wells and Coppersmith 1994).

3.7 East Compostela Valley (ECV) segment

The East Compostela Valley (ECV) segment is the shortest Philippine fault segment in eastern Mindanao (Figure 2). It bounds the western edge of the Eastern Mindanao Ridge and trends almost north-south. Further to the south of this segment, a lineament was identified from satellite images but aerial photo interpretation revealed that no evidence of recent faulting can be identified (Perez et al. 2015). The mapped fault trace is about 20-km-long and is capable of generating a M_w 6.6 earthquake (Wells and Coppersmith 1994).

3.8 Caraga River segment

The Caraga River segment is located at the southern end of the CCV segment. It started in the north with a 5-km-wide restraining step from CCV segment (Figure 2). This segment is manifested by a continuous fault scarp located at the eastern edge of a ridge and almost coincides with the Caraga River before it extends to Eastern Mindanao Ridge. The fault is 35-km-long and generally strikes $N30^{\circ}$ - 40° W. Offset creeks were identified from aerial photographs and at the southern end of the segment a series of en echelon steps (right and left steps) were mapped that ranges from 0.5 to 2 km wide (Perez et al. 2015). Historical seismicity along this segment indicates that there is no historical surface-rupturing earthquake that may be attributed to this segment. The 35-km-long Caraga River segment may generate a M_w 6.9 earthquake (Wells and Coppersmith 1994) if the entire segment will rupture.

3.9 Mati segment

Mati segment branches off to the right on the middle portion of Caraga River segment (Figure 2). This segment traverses the Eastern Mindanao Ridge for about 15 km and bounds the eastern edge of the Maragusan Valley. The fault trends $N10^{\circ}$ - 15° W and cuts young alluvial fans in the valley's eastern edge. Continuous tectonic scarps for about 3 km were also identified (Perez et al. 2015). The fault trace continues for about 55 km traversing the southern end of the Eastern Mindanao Ridge. Perez et al. (2015) mapped tectonic geomorphic features such as offset creek, springs, sag ponds and pressure ridges that indicate recency of surface-rupturing earthquakes. The termination of this fault is located in Mati City wherein branching of the fault and changes in the strike were mapped.

A review of historical and instrumental seismicity and paleoseismic results by Perez and Tsutsumi (in preparation) revealed that no surface-rupturing earthquakes have occurred in

this segment for the past 400 years. If the 60-km-long Mati segment ruptures, this segment will generate a M_w 7.1 earthquake (Wells and Coppersmith 1994).

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

We have described briefly the nine geometric segments of the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao that may rupture independently during large magnitude earthquakes. These fault segments ranges from 20 to 100-km-long and is capable of generating a M_w 6.6 to M_w 7.4 earthquake. Figure 2 and Table 1 shows the surface length of each segment and the magnitude of the maximum credible earthquake for each segment based on the empirical relationship between surface-rupture length and magnitude proposed by Wells and Coppersmith (1994).

Our fault segmentation studies revealed that most of the Philippine fault segments in eastern Mindanao are capable of generating $M_w > 7$ earthquakes except for the ECV segment (M_w 6.6), the Nabunturan segment (M_w 6.7) and the Caraga River segment (M_w 6.7). Surigao segment is the longest segment (100 km) and is capable to generate a M_w 7.4 earthquake. This segment ruptured its entire length during the 1879 M_w 7.4 Surigao earthquake. The second longest segment (65 km) is the Agusan Marsh segment and can generate a M_w 7.2 earthquake. Four segments (CCV segment: 60 km; Mati segment: 55 km; WCV segment: 55 km and Esperanza segment: 50 km) is capable of generating a M_w 7.1 earthquake. The other two historical surface-rupturing earthquake, the 1891 M_s 7.2 Davao earthquake and the 1893 M_s 7.3 Monkayo earthquake, roughly coincide with our suggested maximum credible earthquake of the most probable source fault of these historical earthquakes (the WCV and CCV segments respectively). Out of the nine segments, three segments have already ruptured during the historical time or for the past 400 years (Surigao, WCV and CCV segments).

The probability of large earthquake is high along the six segments – the Esperanza, Agusan Marsh, Nabunturan, ECV, Caraga River and Mati segments – that have not ruptured during historical times. This fact may also indicate probable seismic gaps along the Philippine fault in eastern Mindanao. Compared to Surigao and CCV segments, paleoseismic results along the Mati segments indicates that this segment has longer recurrence interval compared to the two segments. With these assumptions, no historical surface-rupturing earthquakes and longer recurrence interval, the probability is high that the six segments could generate surface-rupturing earthquake in the future. These earthquakes may result to very strong ground shaking that may greatly affect Mindanao Island. The Surigao, CCV and WCV have low probability to have surface-rupturing earthquake in the immediate future because these segments have already ruptured in the past 200 years.

The proposed segmentation and maximum credible earthquake is valid only if individual segments move independently. As discussed in the introduction part of this paper, multiple segments may rupture together resulting to larger magnitude and stronger ground shaking compared to our proposed magnitude and surface-rupture length. These scenario may happen and we suggest that more paleoseismic trenches be excavated along the different segments to identify the history of the surface-rupturing earthquakes and to identify the segments that may move together (temporal fault segmentation). The information generated by our study is a very important input in assessing the seismic risk in Mindanao Island and a great contribution on active faults research in the Philippines.

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ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Jeffrey S. Perez is a Supervising Science Research Specialist and a Geologist from the Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology – Department of Science and Technology (PHIVOLCS-DOST). He is a BS Geology graduate from University of the Philippines and a Master of Engineering Major in Civil and Environmental Engineering graduate from Saitama University, Japan. He may be contacted at PHIVOLCS Bldg., C.P. Garcia Ave., UP Diliman Campus, Quezon City, 1101 Philippines. Tel/Fax: (63 2) 426-1468 loc. 128 and (63 2) 927-4524. Email: jeffrey.perez@phivolcs.dost.gov.ph.

Hiroyuki Tsutsumi is an Associate Professor from the Department of Geophysics, Graduate School of Science, Kyoto University. He may be contacted at Department of Geophysics, Kyoto University, Kitashirakawa-oiwake-cho, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8502, Japan. Email: tsutsumh@kugi.kyoto-u.ac.jp.

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